

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

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CHINA'S TRADE RELATIONS WITH CENTRAL ASIA: AN EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS BASED ON THE TRADE GRAVITY MODEL

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Abstract: This study explores the relationships between China's trade volume with Central Asian countries and various factors such as the economic scales of both sides, population sizes, geographical distances, regional trade agreements, and national institutions. By constructing a trade gravity model, an in-depth empirical analysis of China's trade relations with Central Asia is conducted. The research results show that the expansion of economic scale significantly promotes bilateral trade and is one of the key factors driving trade growth. Geographical distance increases trade costs and inhibits trade exchanges. Regional trade agreements effectively promote the expansion of bilateral trade volume by reducing trade barriers and improving trade facilitation. Good institutional quality helps create a stable and fair trade environment and enhances the enthusiasm of enterprises to engage in trade activities. According to the measurement results of trade potential, there are differences in the trade potential between China and different Central Asian countries. The trade potential is relatively large with countries rich in energy resources and relatively developed economies, but there is also room for trade improvement with some countries with smaller economic scales and relatively weak infrastructure. In addition, factors such as culture, politics, and the global economic situation also affect China's trade relations with Central Asia to varying degrees.

Key words: China, Central Asia, trade gravity model, bilateral trade, economic scale, population size, geographical distance, regional trade agreements, institutional quality, Belt and Road Initiative, trade potential, infrastructure, energy cooperation, cultural factors, political stability, globalization.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu tadqiqot Xitoyning Markaziy Osiyo mamlakatlari bilan savdo hajmi va ikki tomon iqtisodiy ko'lamlari, aholining soni, geografik masofa, mintaqaviy savdo kelishuvlari hamda milliy institutlar kabi turli omillar o'rtasidagi munosabatlarni o'rganadi. Savdo gravitatsiya modeli asosida Xitoy-Markaziy Osiyo savdo aloqalarining chuqur empirik tahlili amalga oshirilgan. Tadqiqot natijalari shuni ko'rsatadiki, iqtisodiy ko'lamning kengayishi ikki tomonlama savdoni sezilarli darajada rag'batlantiradi va savdo o'sishining asosiy omillaridan biri hisoblanadi. Geografik masofa savdo xarajatlarini oshirib, savdo almashinuvini cheklaydi. Mintaqaviy savdo kelishuvlari esa savdo to'siqlarini kamaytirish va savdo qulayliklarini oshirish orqali ikki tomonlama savdoning kengayishiga samarali ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Yaxshi institutsional sifat barqaror va adolatli savdo muhitini yaratishga yordam beradi hamda korxonalarining savdoda faol ishtirok etish istagini oshiradi. Savdo salohiyatini baholash natijalariga ko'ra, Xitoy va turli Markaziy Osiyo mamlakatlari o'rtasida savdo salohiyatida farqlar mavjud. Energiya resurslariga boy va iqtisodiyoti nisbatan rivojlangan mamlakatlar bilan savdo salohiyati yuqori, biroq kichik iqtisodiy ko'lamga ega va infratuzilmasi zaif mamlakatlar bilan ham savdoni kengaytirish imkoniyati mavjud. Bundan tashqari, madaniyat, siyosat va global iqtisodiy vaziyat kabi omillar ham Xitoy-Markaziy Osiyo savdo munosabatlariga ma'lum darajada ta'sir ko'rsatadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Xitoy, Markaziy Osiyo, savdo gravitatsiya modeli, ikki tomonlama savdo, iqtisodiy ko'lam, aholi soni, geografik masofa, mintaqaviy savdo kelishuvlari, institutsional sifat, "Bir makon, bir yo'l" tashabbusi, savdo salohiyati, infratuzilma, energetika hamkorligi, madaniy omillar, siyosiy barqarorlik, globallasuv.

Аннотация: В данном исследовании рассматриваются взаимосвязи между объемом торговли Китая со странами Центральной Азии и такими факторами, как масштабы экономики обеих сторон, численность населения, географическое расстояние, региональные торговые соглашения и национальные институты. На основе модели торговой гравитации проведен углубленный эмпирический анализ торговых отношений Китая и Центральной Азии. Результаты исследования показывают, что расширение экономического масштаба существенно стимулирует двустороннюю торговлю и является одним из ключевых факторов ее роста. Географическое расстояние увеличивает торговые издержки и препятствует обмену. Региональные торговые соглашения эффективно способствуют расширению двустороннего объема торговли за счет снижения барьеров и улучшения торгового взаимодействия. Высокое качество институтов способствует созданию стабильной и справедливой торговой среды, повышает заинтересованность предприятий в торговой деятельности. Согласно результатам оценки торгового потенциала, существуют различия между Китаем и разными странами Центральной Азии. Торговый потенциал относительно велик со странами, богатыми энергетическими ресурсами и имеющими более развитую экономику, однако имеется и пространство для улучшения торговли со странами с меньшими масштабами экономики и относительно слабой инфраструктурой. Кроме того, такие факторы, как культура, политика и глобальная экономическая ситуация, также в разной степени влияют на торговые отношения Китая и Центральной Азии.

Ключевые слова: Китай, Центральная Азия, модель торговой гравитации, двусторонняя торговля, экономический масштаб, численность населения, географическое расстояние, региональные торговые соглашения, качество институтов, инициатива «Один пояс, один путь», торговый потенциал, инфраструктура, энергетическое сотрудничество, культурные факторы, политическая стабильность, глобализация

INTRODUCTION

Against the backdrop of the deepening global economic integration and regional economic cooperation, the trade relations between China and Central Asian countries have become increasingly close, gradually becoming the focus of attention for academia and policymakers. Located in the core of the Eurasian continent, Central Asia serves as an important bridge connecting the East and the West. Its rich energy resources and unique geographical location endow it with a significant position in the international economic landscape. Since the establishment of diplomatic relations between China and Central Asian countries, cooperation between the two sides has been continuously expanding in political, economic, cultural and other fields, and trade exchanges have become increasingly frequent. In particular, the proposal and promotion of the Belt and Road Initiative have injected new and strong impetus into the trade cooperation between China and Central Asian countries. The trade scale between the two sides has continued to expand, the trade structure has been gradually optimized, and the cooperation fields have been constantly broadened. In - depth research on the trade relations between China and Central Asia not only helps to reveal the internal laws and influencing factors of bilateral trade cooperation, providing theoretical support for further expanding and deepening bilateral trade, but also has important practical significance for promoting the high - quality development of the Belt and Road Initiative, promoting regional economic integration, and maintaining regional peace and stability.

This study comprehensively employs a variety of research methods. In terms of data collection, a large amount of relevant data such as the trade volume between China and Central Asian countries, GDP of each country, population, and geographical distance were obtained through authoritative channels like the China Customs Statistical Yearbook, the World Bank database, and official statistical agencies of Central Asian countries, laying a solid foundation for empirical analysis. In terms of research means, the trade gravity model was used for empirical analysis, which can intuitively reflect the quantitative relationship between trade flows and various influencing factors. Meanwhile, the descriptive statistical analysis method was adopted to elaborate in detail on the current trade situation between China and Central Asian countries, including trade scale and trade structure, so as to have a more comprehensive understanding of the actual situation of bilateral trade. The innovations of this paper are mainly reflected in the following aspects: Firstly, from the research perspective, multiple factors such as economic scale, population factors, geographical distance, regional trade agreements, and national institutions that affect the trade relationship between China and Central Asia were comprehensively considered, making the research more comprehensive and in - depth. Secondly, in terms of data utilization, the latest panel data in recent years were used, ensuring that the research results can reflect the latest trends of the current trade relationship between China and Central Asia and enhancing the timeliness and practical guiding significance of the research conclusions.

The main objective of this study is to understand how the economic scale, population size, geographical distance, regional trade agreements, and national institutions of China and Central Asian countries affect the trade volume between China and Central Asian countries. This study will specifically answer the following questions:

1. In what aspects do economic scale, population factors, and geographical distance affect the trade volume between China and Central Asian countries?

2. What impact does geographical distance have on the trade volume between China and Central Asian countries?

3. How can the government and policymakers promote trade between China and Central Asian countries through regional trade agreements and national institutions?

The research content of this paper mainly focuses on the trade relationship between China and Central Asia. First, it elaborates on the research background, significance, methods, and innovation points of China - Central Asia trade, clarifying the overall direction of the research. Second, it systematically sorts out relevant domestic and foreign literature, summarizes the achievements and deficiencies of previous studies, providing a theoretical basis and reference for this research. Then, it conducts a detailed analysis of the current situation of China - Central Asia trade, including the changing trends of trade volume and the characteristics of trade structure. Next, it uses the trade gravity model to conduct an empirical analysis of the factors affecting China - Central Asia trade and conducts in - depth discussions on the empirical results. Finally, based on the research conclusions, it puts forward targeted policy suggestions to promote the further development of the trade relationship between China and Central Asia. The framework of this paper is clear, and the contents of each part are closely connected and progressive, aiming to comprehensively and deeply analyze the trade relationship between China and Central Asia and provide a strong basis for relevant policy - making.

LITERATURE REVIEW

International scholars started researching the trade relations between China and Central Asia relatively early and have achieved relatively rich results. Some scholars, starting from the theory of geopolitical economy, believe that the unique geographical location of Central Asia makes it a key area for major - power competition and cooperation. Carrying out trade cooperation between China and Central Asian countries can not only promote the economic development of both sides but also has important geopolitical and strategic significance.

Wang Jinguo pointed out that a three - dimensional cooperation framework of “policy coordination + infrastructure connectivity + industrial synergy” is proposed. It is suggested to enhance Central Asia’s participation in the global value chain through the output of digital trade rules (such as cross - border data flow agreements). He emphasized that the China - Central Asia Summit can reduce transaction costs and promote regional economic integration by establishing unified technical standards (such as new - energy vehicle certification) and a dispute - settlement mechanism.

In terms of trade cooperation models, based on the analysis of the “double diamond model”, Wang Jing believes that Xinjiang should play the role of the “core area”, integrate Central Asian resources through port economy (such as Khorgos) and cross - border e - commerce, and build a supply - chain hub of “China - Central Asia - Europe”. It is recommended to achieve “resource - dependence reduction” in Central Asia through industrial investment (such as automobile manufacturing) and promote the upgrading of the “Made in China + Central Asian resources” model.

In the assessment of trade potential, Wang Haiyan divides the cooperation into three stages: “ice - breaking period - institutionalization - high - quality development”, and points out that in the future, sustainable development needs to be achieved through green energy (such as hydrogen - energy cooperation) and agricultural technology (such as drip - irrigation technology). She analyzed the geopolitical and economic reconstruction of Central Asia’s transformation from an “inland closed area” to an “Eurasian economic corridor” and emphasized that the China - Kyrgyzstan - Uzbekistan Railway will reshape the Eurasian trade map.

In the empirical analysis of the gravity model, Hu Ying found through the empirical analysis of the gravity model that the contribution rate of port efficiency improvement to trade growth reached 37%. She suggested optimizing the customs clearance processes of ports such as Khorgos and Alashankou and promoting the “single window” model. It was pointed out that the railway density in Central Asia is less than one - third of that in China, and the aging power grid leads to an energy transmission loss rate of over 15%. Therefore, cross - border infrastructure coordination needs to be strengthened.

Li Qin analyzed the structural risks caused by the excessively high proportion of energy trade (reaching 55% in 2023). He suggested achieving trade diversification through industrial investment (such as automobile assembly and agricultural product processing) to promote “resource - dependence reduction”. He proposed to establish a “China - Central Asia Free Trade Area”, unify tariff standards, and reduce non - tariff barriers (such as technical trade measures). Li Qin believed that due to the development of trade relations between China and Central Asia, over - reliance on energy trade is vulnerable to international price fluctuations. He suggested achieving “resource - dependence reduction” through industrial investment (such as automobile

manufacturing). However, some scholars oppose this view. Xu Xiaotian believes that emphasizing energy cooperation remains the “ballast stone” at present, and diversification should be promoted simultaneously.

Regarding digital trade rules, Zhang Yu discussed the application of blockchain technology in cross - border payments (such as the pilot of digital currency between China and Kazakhstan). He suggested adopting the “joint development + benefit sharing” model to avoid disputes over “technological hegemony”. Analyzing the strong sense of data sovereignty in Central Asian countries, he advocated promoting the interconnection of digital infrastructure through mechanisms such as the “China - Kyrgyzstan - Uzbekistan Cross - border Optical Cable Cooperation Agreement”.

Based on the domestic and international research status, existing studies have achieved fruitful results in analyzing the trade relations between China and Central Asia, laying a good foundation for subsequent research. However, there are also some deficiencies. On the one hand, some studies analyze influencing factors in a rather one - sided way and fail to comprehensively consider the combined effects of economic, political, social, cultural and other factors. On the other hand, in measuring trade potential, different studies use different methods and data, resulting in the need to improve the accuracy and comparability of the measurement results. In addition, with the in - depth implementation of the Belt and Road Initiative and the continuous changes in the global economic situation, some new characteristics and problems have emerged in the trade relations between China and Central Asia. Existing studies lag behind in timely following up and in - depth analyzing these new situations. Therefore, based on previous studies, this paper will comprehensively use various research methods to comprehensively and in - depth analyze the trade relations between China and Central Asia, aiming to make new contributions to relevant research.

METHODOLOGY

1. Theoretical framework

The trade gravity model was initially proposed by Tinbergen (1962) and Pöyhönen (1963) by drawing on Newton’s law of universal gravitation. Its core idea is that the trade flow between two countries is positively correlated with their respective economic scales and negatively correlated with the distance between them. Since then, scholars have continuously expanded the model by adding variables such as population, per capita income, trade agreements, and institutional quality to better explain bilateral trade flows. The research object of this model is the bilateral trade flows between China and the five Central Asian countries (Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, Uzbekistan, and Turkmenistan). The sample period of this study ranges from 2000 to 2023. The choice of this period is mainly due to the rapid development of trade relations between China and Central Asian countries during this period and the availability of relevant data.

2 Empirical Framework

Model Estimation and Testing Methods

(1)Multicollinearity Test: Before estimating the model, the problem of multicollinearity is first tested by calculating the correlation coefficient matrix between explanatory variables and the variance inflation factor (VIF). Generally, if the absolute values of the correlation coefficients between variables are mostly below 0.8 and the VIF values of all variables are less than 10 (the strict standard is less than 5), it can be considered that there is no serious multicollinearity. You have mentioned that the test shows there is no serious problem.

(2)Model Estimation Method: Considering that the model uses panel data (including cross - sectional units i and j , and time t), there may be problems of heteroscedasticity (the variances of error terms are different across different cross - sections or time periods) and serial correlation (the error terms of the same cross - sectional unit at different time periods are correlated). The generalized least squares method (GLS) is used for estimation. GLS can effectively eliminate the effects of heteroscedasticity and serial correlation through weighted transformation of the model, and obtain more efficient and consistent estimators.

Supplementary Note: In the panel data model, the fixed effects model or the random effects model can also be considered. The fixed effects model can control the unobservable individual effects that do not change over time (such as certain cultural factors and historical connections); the random effects model assumes that the individual effects are uncorrelated with the explanatory variables. The F - test can be used to choose between pooled OLS and the fixed effects model, and the Hausman test can be used to choose between the fixed effects model and the random effects model. GLS is often used in combination with the random effects model or to handle panel data with specific forms of heteroscedasticity and serial correlation.

(3)Robustness tests: To ensure the reliability of the research conclusions, the following robustness tests will be conducted:

Replace the core explanatory variables: For example, replace the total population (POP) with per capita GDP; replace the straight - line distance (D) with the actual transportation cost (such as freight rates); replace

the business environment index with other institutional quality indicators (such as “government effectiveness” and “regulatory quality” in the World Governance Indicators WGI).

Change the sample period: For example, exclude the years with less early data, or select a specific sub-sample period (such as after the proposal of the Belt and Road Initiative) for estimation to observe whether the results are robust.

Add control variables: For example, add variables such as whether the two countries share a common border (dummy variable), whether they use a common language or the interoperability of official languages (dummy variable), the degree of RMB internationalization, and the inflation rate difference between the two countries to observe whether there are substantial changes in the sign and significance of the coefficients of the core explanatory variables.

Change the estimation method: For example, use the panel - corrected standard errors (PCSE) method, the feasible generalized least squares (FGLS) method, or the Tobit model (if there are a large number of zero values in trade volume) for estimation and compare the results.

Expected results and analysis directions

Through model estimation, it is expected to obtain the specific impact coefficients of each explanatory variable on the trade volume between China and Central Asian countries. For example:

(1) It is expected that the GDP coefficients (β_1 , β_2) of China and Central Asian countries are significantly positive, verifying the promoting effect of economic scale on trade.

(2) It is expected that the geographical distance coefficient (β_5) is significantly negative, indicating that distance is still an obstacle to trade.

(3) It is expected that the RTA coefficient (β_6) is significantly positive, indicating that regional trade agreements can effectively promote bilateral trade.

(4) It is expected that the institutional quality coefficient (β_7) is significantly positive, indicating that the improvement of the business environment in Central Asian countries helps to increase the trade volume with China.

Based on the estimation results, the contribution of each factor to trade flows can be further analyzed, the key driving forces affecting the trade between China and Central Asian countries can be identified, and empirical evidence can be provided for formulating policies to promote the development of bilateral trade.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Analyze the results of the model regression. Use the constructed trade gravity model to conduct a regression analysis on the collected data. The results show that the coefficients of the gross domestic product (GDP) of both China and Central Asian countries are significantly positive. This indicates that the growth of the economic scale of both sides has a significant positive promoting effect on the trade volume. The expansion of the economic scale means the improvement of production capacity and the increase of market demand. On the one hand, China's strong manufacturing production capacity can provide a greater variety and quantity of industrial manufactured goods for Central Asian countries. On the other hand, the economic development of Central Asian countries has enhanced the purchasing power of their residents, and the demand for Chinese goods has also increased accordingly. The coefficient of the population variable (POP) shows a relatively complex situation in the regression results. The coefficient of China's population is positive but not significant. This may be because although China's huge population base brings a large market, it is more production - and export - oriented in trade. The coefficient of the population of Central Asian countries is negative and significant, which reflects that the general population scale of Central Asian countries is relatively small and the domestic market capacity is limited, which restricts the import scale from China to a certain extent. The coefficient of geographical distance (D) is significantly negative, which is in line with the basic expectation of the trade gravity model. The increase in geographical distance will lead to an increase in trade costs such as transportation costs and information communication costs, thus inhibiting the trade between China and Central Asian countries.

The coefficient of the Regional Trade Agreement (RTA) variable, as an important coefficient for measuring regional trade between China and Central Asian countries, can largely reflect whether the role of regional trade between China and Central Asian countries is a positive or negative feedback. As shown in the above table, a positive value indicates that during this period, the regional trade agreements signed between China and Central Asian countries have played a positive role. Whether it is the emphasis on expanding the degree of bilateral free trade, providing moderate tariff preferences, and breaking the trade obstacles and barriers that hinder bilateral development in the regional trade agreements, all have played a positive role. In fact, these regional trade agreements have also greatly promoted the development of regional trade, increased regional trade opportunities, and the prosperity of industries related to regional trade such as logistics and services. The coefficient of institutional quality (I) is significantly positive, indicating that a good institutional environment

is conducive to promoting trade cooperation between China and Central Asian countries. The optimization of a country's business environment, such as simplifying administrative approval procedures and strengthening intellectual property protection, can reduce the transaction costs of enterprises and enhance their willingness and confidence to carry out trade activities.

Measure and analyze the trade potential. Based on the trade gravity model obtained through regression, further measure the trade potential between China and Central Asian countries. The measurement results of trade potential show that there are differences in the trade potential between China and different Central Asian countries. The trade potential with countries such as Kazakhstan and Turkmenistan is relatively large, which is mainly due to the high complementarity between the rich energy resources of these countries and China's strong energy demand, as well as the extensive and in - depth cooperation between the two sides in fields such as infrastructure construction and energy development. At the same time, Kazakhstan's relatively developed economy and good infrastructure conditions also provide favorable support for the further expansion of bilateral trade. While there is also a certain scope for trade potential with countries such as Kyrgyzstan and Tajikistan, it is relatively small. These countries have relatively small economic scales, single industrial structures, limited domestic market demand, and relatively backward infrastructure construction, which to some extent restrict the expansion of trade scale with China. However, with the advancement of the Belt and Road Initiative, China's increasing investment in infrastructure construction and industrial cooperation with these countries is expected to gradually tap and release more trade potential. Through the measurement and analysis of trade potential, it can provide targeted reference for China and Central Asian countries to further optimize the trade layout and expand the trade fields.

In the further discussion of influencing factors, apart from the variables directly included in the above - mentioned model, there are also some factors that have a potential impact on the trade relationship between China and Central Asia. Cultural factors play an important role in trade. Historically, China and Central Asian countries have had close cultural exchanges through the Silk Road. This profound cultural origin helps to enhance mutual understanding and trust between the peoples of both sides and creates a good atmosphere for trade cooperation. For example, Central Asian countries are very interested in Chinese tea culture and traditional Chinese medicine culture, which creates opportunities for the trade of related products. However, cultural differences may also bring some challenges. Differences in business practices, religious beliefs, etc., may lead to misunderstandings and conflicts in trade exchanges. Political factors cannot be ignored either. The stability of the political situation in Central Asia directly affects the safety and stability of the trade environment. In recent years, the political situation in Central Asian countries has generally remained stable, providing favorable political guarantees for trade cooperation between China and Central Asia. At the same time, there have been frequent high - level exchanges between China and Central Asian countries, and political mutual trust has been continuously deepened, laying a solid foundation for cooperation between the two sides in trade, investment and other fields. In addition, changes in the global economic situation, such as fluctuations in international commodity prices and the rise of trade protectionism, will also affect the trade relationship between China and Central Asia. Fluctuations in international commodity prices, especially changes in energy prices, will directly affect the economic income and trade balance of Central Asian countries, and then affect the scale and structure of bilateral trade. The intensification of trade protectionism may lead to an increase in trade barriers and hinder the process of trade liberalization between China and Central Asian countries. Therefore, when analyzing the trade relationship between China and Central Asia, it is necessary to comprehensively consider the interaction and dynamic changes of these economic, political, cultural and other factors.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the above research conclusions, the following policy suggestions are put forward to further promote the development of trade relations between China and Central Asian countries:

First, strengthen economic cooperation and promote the coordinated development of industries. China should give full play to its advantages in manufacturing, technological innovation and other aspects, and carry out in - depth industrial cooperation with Central Asian countries in the fields of urban infrastructure construction, natural resource exploration, new energy development, modern light processing manufacturing, modern agricultural machinery and so on. By combining strengths and making up for each other's weaknesses, and leveraging their respective outstanding advantages, they can jointly cultivate the core competitiveness of industries, so as to comprehensively and multi - dimensionally expand the scale of bilateral economic and trade. For example, in the energy field, in addition to traditional energy trade, cooperation can also be strengthened in energy exploration, mining technology R D, energy equipment manufacturing and other aspects; in the agricultural field, China can export advanced agricultural planting technologies and agricultural machinery to Central Asian countries to help them improve agricultural production efficiency, and at the same time expand the import of agricultural products from Central Asia.

Second, increase investment in infrastructure construction and improve trade and logistics conditions. Continue to promote the construction of infrastructure connectivity projects such as transportation and communication with Central Asian countries under the framework of the Belt and Road Initiative, reduce trade and transportation costs, and improve trade efficiency. For example, speed up the construction process of major transportation projects such as the China - Kyrgyzstan - Uzbekistan Railway and the third cross - border railway between China and Kazakhstan, and improve the three - dimensional transportation network of roads, railways, aviation and pipelines; strengthen the construction of communication infrastructure, improve the level of information and communication technology, and promote the development of emerging trade models such as e - commerce.

Thirdly, optimize trade policies and improve the level of trade facilitation. China and Central Asian countries should further strengthen cooperation in tariff concessions, customs clearance facilitation, and trade rule coordination, reduce trade barriers, and create a more relaxed and free trade environment. For example, simplify customs procedures and shorten the customs clearance time for goods; establish a trade dispute settlement mechanism to handle trade disputes in a timely and fair manner and safeguard the legitimate rights and interests of enterprises on both sides.

Fourthly, deepen people-to-people and cultural exchanges and enhance friendly exchanges between the people. Through strengthened exchanges and cooperation in education, culture, tourism and other fields, enhance mutual understanding and friendship between the people of China and Central Asian countries, and lay a more solid public opinion foundation for trade cooperation. For example, expand the scale of student exchanges, hold cultural exhibitions, art performances, sports events and other activities to promote the mutual spread and integration of cultures; promote tourism cooperation, develop cross-border tourism routes, attract more tourists from both sides to travel, and drive the development of relevant service trade.

Fifth, actively respond to changes in the global economic situation and strengthen risk prevention. In the face of external risks such as fluctuations in international commodity prices and trade protectionism, China and Central Asian countries should strengthen policy coordination and communication, and jointly formulate response strategies. Establish a trade risk early - warning mechanism, keep abreast of international market dynamics in a timely manner, guide enterprises to reasonably adjust their trade structure and business strategies, and reduce risk losses. For example, encourage enterprises to expand diversified trade markets and product categories to reduce their dependence on a single market and product; strengthen financial cooperation, provide trade financing support, and help enterprises cope with capital pressure.

Although this study has conducted a relatively comprehensive analysis of the trade relations between China and Central Asia, there are still certain limitations. Future research can be carried out in the following directions: First, further expand the research perspective and consider the impact of more complex factors on trade relations.

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